

Profile of Critical Thinking Skills on Fluid Mechanics Material by Senior High School Students in Makassar City

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 29, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Academic Argumentative Essay, Time Variable, Writing, Discourse Measures</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4445379</p>	<p><i>To confirm the most effective time allotment for IELTS test-takers, this study is carried out to examine how different time allotments (30 or 50 minutes) affect students' writing skills. This study used a range of measures to assess the test takers' writing. Participants were also interviewed about their perceptions under the two-timing conditions. The study revealed that students' writing skills only increased concerning fluency under the longer (30-min) time condition. Complexity also improved, yet it was very marginal, thus making it hard to conclude. Despite the overall insignificant differences of students' scores under the two-timing conditions, students were confident and believed that they did a better essay under the more extended time allotment. The study confirms that test-takers could do writing section in IELTS better in a longer time allotment than those given a shorter time allotment. Practicality seems to be the most convincing reason which causes test providers to set limited time for the test administration, specifically for academic writing tasks. As far as we are concerned, a few studies are specifically focused on investigating the effects of time allotments for argumentative writing tasks, this work is an attempt to fill in this gap.</i></p>

Introduction

It is widely recognized that there are at least two types of test items generally used in an educational environment to assess students' competence and performance. Competence refers to the students' knowledge required to enable them to do something properly (Bahar, 2013), (Arafah, B., Thayyib, M., Kaharuddin, & Sahib, H. 2020)). On the other hand, performance refers to the students' ability to do something using their competence (Andi, K., & Arafah, B, 2017), (Kaharuddin, Ahmad, D, Mardiana, Rusni (2020). The two types of tests cover: *the first*, assessing students' ability or skills by getting them to select the correct response from a set of possible responses such as multiple-choice, true-false, as well as matching items, and *the second*, assessing the students' ability by allowing them to construct a response on their own as seen in an essay or short-answer items. Between the two types of tests, the second type (particularly essay test) seems to be more commonly used in many standardized testing (Lovett et al., 2010). Even if the essay test is more dominant used than a selected-response test. This type of test still has at least two important limitations such as measurement of comprehensive thinking ability (Lee, W. 2010, Arafah, B. & Hasyim, M. 2019) and time allotment (D E Powers, 2005). The time allotment significantly affects the number of sentences or texts that the test takers can write. This fact may also affect their scores because the number of text written by a test taker is highly correlated to his/her essay length and quality ((Hopkins, 1998), (D E Powers, 2005), (Gregg et al., 2007), (Maharani, 2018), (Lovett et al., 2010)).

The time allocation for standardized essay tests is relatively short, generally between 10 and 15 minutes (Lovett et al., 2010). The minimization of the time allotment is intended to assist language test providers with more practical test administration and assessment. However, this decision has been questioned whether shorter time allotments could give test takers adequate time and an ideal opportunity to demonstrate their natural writing ability. Surprisingly, few in-depth types of research have conducted to directly examine the effects of time allotment on test-takers' writing skills. Many types of research are simply focused on examining the degree to which test scores on are the product of working quickly (Lovett et al., 2010). In this regard, this current study has been carried out and is aimed at not only quantitatively investigating the effect of using two different timing conditions (30 and 50 minutes) on test-takers' achievement in test scores for argumentative academic writing, but also descriptively investigating the test takers' perceptions of the two-timing conditions. Therefore, this study works explicitly on examining two crucial research questions, namely: First, do students' scores of writing tasks differ between the long (50-min) and low (30-min) timing conditions? Second, what are the students' perceptions of the differences between the two different timing conditions?

Literature review

Many studies on augmentative writing have been conducted earlier which center on different aspects such as the importance of time extension (Crawford, L., Helwig, R., & Tindal, G. 2004), the effect of time constraints (Chan, W. F. (2007), issues in writing assessment (Applebee, A. N. 2011), the effect of techniques in writing (Vonna, Y., Mukminatien, N., & Laksmi, E. D. 2015), the effect of time constraint (Lee, J. 2019). However, a few studies specifically focused on investigating the effects of time allotments for argumentative writing tasks are found for the last ten years. One of the earlier studies that has investigated the issue is the one conducted by Biola, (1982). Biola administered an argumentative writing task to 96 university students between a 45- and 120-minute time condition and found that the students under the longer time allowance performed significantly better than those under the shorter time condition; Biola in this study controlled the topic assignment variable. With this finding, the author claimed that with the two-hour time limit, all of the students could have the same chances to demonstrate their best writing performance.

Quite similarly, assigned 304 college students to write two essays under the short (30-min) and long (60-min) time conditions. The authors found that allowing more time could result in increased writing performance (Donald E Powers & Fowles, 1996). Examinees were also reported to prefer the longer over the shorter time condition. In a more recent study, also reported that test-takers were able to significantly generate more complex argumentative essays on untimed essays compared to timed essays (Lu, 2011). The author conducted a corpus-based study on 3,678 essays produced by Chinese college students from nine different institutions.

Examining writing scores between the long (55-minute) and short (30-minute) time condition, Elder, Knoch, and Zhang (2009) showed that participants' mean scores were higher in all of the measures of writing fluency, content, and form as well as the average total score. Nonetheless, the differences were not found to be statistically significantly different, thus leading the authors to the claim that shortening the time allocation for argumentative essay tasks cannot be assumed to generate a less valid indicator of examinees' academic writing.

Comparing essays written in class (60 minutes) and essays written at home (10-14 days), (Kroll, n.d.) analyzed 100 essays by 25 university students and found that students writing at home appeared to generate higher overall mean on a syntactic level and global-level holistic score. However, the differences were only marginal, indicating no statistically significant differences between these two-time conditions. With a similar finding, (Caudery, 1990) showed no significant differences in 24 adolescent students' writing performance on argumentative essays under time-restricted and non-time-restricted conditions both in terms of language and organization measures and in terms of total scores.

More recently, (Shehadeh et al., 2009) investigated how two different time conditions (30 and 55 minutes) could impact students' performance in writing argumentative essays. The authors showed that students' scores in fluency, content, and form, as well as the total score, were rated higher under the more extended time allocation. Yet, none of the reported differences was statistically significant. Detailed discourse analysis revealed that participants were able to produce a more significant number of words within the more extended time condition, indicating students were more fluent when given more time. Other measures (e.g., accuracy, complexity, cohesion) were not found to put participants with a more generous time allowance at an advantage. Additionally, Knoch and Elder also explored examinees' perceptions and showed that participants preferred the longer time conditions in that they could have more time for planning and revising.

Methods

A. Participants

Eight samples of writing were collected from four participants, all of whom are Indonesians with two females and two males. Ranging in age from 22 to 28 years old, all participants have finished their bachelor's degree except Student 3, who was still in the last semester. Three of them, Student 1, 2, and 4, have sat for an official IELTS test with a writing score of 5.5, 5.5, and 6.5, respectively. Student 2 has taken the tests twice, and her writing score for the first test was 6.5. Student 3 has not taken an official test yet but has sat for a practice test as

part of his IELTS course; his overall band score was 5.5, with 6.0 for the writing section. (The participants' specific information is presented in Table 1.)

Table 1
Participants' information

Participant	Sex	Age	IELTS Writing score	Overall IELTS score
Student 1	Female	25	5.5	6.5
Student 2	Female	22	5.5/6.5	6.0
Student 3	Male	22	6.0	5.5
Student 4	Male	28	6.5	6.0

B. Instruments

To ensure that the topic and genre variables were controlled, two writing tasks used for the current study were both argumentative essays with the topic of technology. The time allowance was set to 30 and 50 minutes for tasks 1 and 2, respectively; both required students to write at least 200 words. (The two writing prompts can be seen in Appendix A.)

Interview. A semi-structured interview is a flexible and informal conversation by using telephone (Longhurst, R. 2003, Schmidt, C. 2004, Arafah, A. N. B., & Setiyawati, D. 2020), which was held with each of the participants after the completion of both tasks. Participants were interviewed about their perceptions of whether they have adequate time to complete both tasks. They were also asked about planning, revising, task or topic difficulty or differences, and finally, their overall impression of the two different time conditions. The interview was conducted in the Indonesian language to ensure detailed answers from the participants. (The questions used for the interview can be seen in Appendix B.)

C. Data Analysis

Discourse-analytic measures. All of the essays were coded for a range of quantitative linguistic measures that included accuracy, fluency, and grammatical complexity, which are T-unit and clause based. In terms of the coding of T-units and clauses, this study followed coding scheme (Cumming et al., 2005). In this case, a T-unit is an independent clause along with its dependent clause(s), and a clause includes both independent and dependent clauses (adverbial, relative, and nominal clauses).

Following (Knoch et al., 2015), (Arafah & Kaharuddin, 2019), the measures of fluency used in this study were the total number of words (W) and the number of T-units (T). The measures of accuracy were the proportion of error-free T-units (EFT/T) and the proportion of error-free clauses (EFC/C). The measures of grammatical complexity were the number of words per T-units (W/T) and the number of clauses per T-unit (C/T).

Concerning the accuracy, errors were counted as errors in morphology (e.g., subject-verb agreement, articles, tenses), in syntax (e.g., missing elements, word order), and in lexis (e.g., word choice). Spelling and punctuation errors were not counted. (The analysis of all of the essays can be seen in Appendix C, and the total calculation of the comparisons of the essays for each time condition is in Appendix D).

IELTS rating criteria. In addition to the discourse-analytic measures above, all of the essays were also marked using the IELTS task 2 writing band descriptors (public version). The measures include task achievement, coherence and cohesion, lexical resource, and grammatical range and accuracy. (The markings of the essays can be seen in Appendix E.)

Semi-structured interview. The results of the interviews were qualitatively analysed and reported based on emerging themes. The themes were specifically divided into participants' beliefs over the adequacy of the time allotments to complete the tasks and how these conditions affect their planning and revising.

Results

Research Question 1: Do students' scores of writing tasks differ between the long (50-min) and short (30-min) time conditions?

To answer the first research question, the participants' scores under the two-time conditions were compared using the discourse measures. Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the fluency measures under the 30 and 50-minute condition. As can be seen within the table, the number of words and T-units appeared to slightly increase in overall mean under the long condition. Thus, it can be said that students were able to produce longer essays within the 50-minute condition.

Table 2

Students' Scores on Fluency Measures Under Short and Long Condition						
Measure	Time limit	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Overall mean
Number of words (W)	30 minutes	271	308	165	165	227.25
	50 minutes	289	337	198	222	261.5
Number of T-units (T)	30 minutes	13	17	9	12	12.75
	50 minutes	17	19	9	14	14.75

Table 3 presents students' scores and overall mean on accuracy measures within the two-time conditions. Mean score comparisons showed that the percentage of both error-free T-units and clauses slightly decreased. Therefore, it can be said that students did not manage to improve the accuracy of their essays regardless of the longer time allowance.

Table 3

Students' Scores on Accuracy Measures Under Short and Long Condition						
Measure	Time limit	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Overall mean
Error-free T-unit ratio (EFT/T)	30 mins	31%	29%	22%	33%	29%
	50 mins	29%	26%	22%	36%	28%
Error-free clause ratio (EFC/C)	30 mins	41%	64%	43%	65%	53%
	50 mins	57%	46%	47%	52%	51%

The measures for complexity generated a different picture as shown in Table 4. The table shows that there was a slight increase in the overall mean of both measures (words per T-units and clauses for T-unit ration).

Table 4

Students' Scores on Complexity Measures Under Short and Long Condition

Measure	Time limit	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Overall mean
Words per T-units (W/T)	30 mins	20.85	18.12	18.33	13.75	17.76
	50 mins	17	17.74	22	15.86	18.15
Clauses per T-unit ratio (C/T)	30 mins	1.69	2.47	1.56	1.42	1.79
	50 mins	1.65	1.84	2.11	1.64	1.81

Thus far, the findings showed that participants produced more words and more grammatically complex essays under the 50-minute condition. However, a slight decrease was found regarding the accuracy as measured by error-free T-units and clauses (see Table 3).

Table 5

Students' Scores on IELTS Analytic Scale Under Short and Long Condition

Measure	Time limit	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Overall mean
Task Achievement	30 mins	7.0	5.5	5.5	6.0	6.0
	50 mins	5.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5
Coherence and Cohesion	30 mins	6.5	6.5	6.0	6.0	6.5
	50 mins	5.5	6.0	6.0	6.5	6.0
Lexical Resource	30 mins	6.5	6.0	5.5	6.0	6.0
	50 mins	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Grammatical Range and Accuracy	30 mins	6.5	7.0	6.5	7.0	7.0
	50 mins	6.5	6.5	6.5	7.0	6.5
Total scores	30 mins	6.5	6.5	6.0	6.5	6.5
	50 mins	6.0	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5

Finally, an analytic rating scale of IELTS for writing task 2 (public version) was used to compare participants' band scores for the measures of task achievement, coherence and cohesion, lexical resource, and grammatical range and accuracy as well as the average writing scores between the long and short time condition. As can be seen in Table 5, the overall means of task achievement elicited a score half a band higher for the 50-minute condition; however, the means of both coherence and cohesion and grammatical range and accuracy showed a slight decrease (half a band lower) for the running condition. The band scores for lexical resources remained stable. The overall means of the average writing scores further confirm that participants' overall band scores did not show any differences under the two-time conditions.

In summary, the results of this study showed that participants were more fluent and able to generate more grammatically, albeit slightly, complex essays under the 50-minute condition. They were also more successful in meeting the criteria for task achievement. In contrast, other discourse measures (e.g., accuracy, coherence and cohesion, lexical resource) resulted in a decrease under the more extended time allocation. The overall mean of the IELTS scale further showed no differences in participants' total band scores under the two-time conditions. In other words, no essential differences were found under the 30 and 50-minute condition.

Research Question 2: What are the participants' perceptions of the differences between the two different time conditions?

To answer the second research question, participants were interviewed about their perceptions of whether they have adequate time to complete both tasks. They were also asked about planning, revising, task or topic difficulty or differences, and finally, their overall impression of the two different time conditions.

Time limit. Three of the participants reported that the time allocation was adequate for them to complete the tasks, both of which required the participants to write at least 200 words. However, one participant (Student 2) mentioned that she could not finish her essay under the 30-minute condition. It is important to note that Student 2 wrote 308 words; this is significantly over the word limit. When informed about this, she said that she did not realize that she had indeed written more than required. Thus far this shows that all of the participants were able to complete the task under the short time condition.

Planning. All of the participants said that they planned for each task; however, they reported different ways of planning because of the different time allowances. Student 1 said that her brainstorming task 1 was different from that of Task 2. Within the short time condition, she was only able to prepare the main topics, whereas, within the long-time condition, she could prepare main ideas along with the supporting details. Similarly, Student 3 mentioned that he spent more time planning with more specific ideas within a more extended time allowance.

Unlike Student 1 and 3, Student 2 reported that her planning for Task 2 required less time because of the topic similarity of the two tasks. Student 4 also stated that he did not consider the two different time conditions to have affected the way he planned. For him, there were no differences in his planning for both task conditions. Hence, the results show that students differed in their planning, owing to the different time conditions.

Revising. Students 1 and 2 said that they did not have adequate time under the shorter time allocation to make any revisions. In contrast, Student 4 mentioned that he could finish each of the tasks under 30 minutes, thus allowing him sufficient time for revising. Quite differently, Student 3 reported that he had indeed more time to revise; however, he said the revision time for Task 1 was limited, yet he had more time revising his essays for Task 2.

Overall impression. Two respondents believed that they performed significantly better under the 50-minute condition. Student 2 believed that she produced a better essay within the more extended time allowance in that she did not finish her essay within the 30-minute condition. Likewise, Student 3 was highly confident that he generated a better essay for a longer time condition because he had more time for planning and revisions.

Surprisingly, Student 1 mentioned that she found Task 2 more difficult because of the topic difference; to her, the time allowance either 30 minutes or 50 minutes was not an issue, yet it was more about the topic that she believed could affect her essays. Lastly, Student 4 stated that he did not find the different time conditions to significantly affect his essay quality because he could finish both of the tasks under 30 minutes.

Discussion

The current study's purpose was to investigate how different time allotments (30 versus 50 minutes) affected students' performance on academic argumentative essays. The findings of the study showed that, based on the overall IELTS writing scores, participants' scores were not found to be significantly different under the two different time allotments. This can be said to be consistent with the findings of (Caudery, 1990), (Shehadeh et al., 2009), and (Kroll, n.d.), all of whom documented marginal differences in scores for essay tasks produced under different time allocations. Thus, the results showed inconsistency with the findings of (Biola, 1982), (Lu, 2011), (Donald E Powers & Fowles, 1996).

Looking at more detailed results of the IELTS rating scale as well as the discourse measures, however, this study revealed that students under the longer time allowance appeared to increase their scores by half a band higher in task achievement. The increased scores were also shown concerning students' fluency (measured via the number of words and T-units) and complexity (measured via words per T-units and clauses per T-unit ratio).

In terms of the increased performance influence, the current findings can be said to be consistent with (Shehadeh et al., 2009) research, which reported that participants' scores under the longer (55-min) condition were statistically significantly better than those under, the shorter (30-min) condition. Concerning the slightly increased scores in grammatical complexity, however, the current study appeared to be inconsistent with Knoch and Elder's findings, which showed that their participants scored lower under the more extended time condition. Thus, the current study regarding complexity could be said to support the findings of (Lu, 2011), who reported students' higher scores for complexity under untimed test conditions.

Consistent with the previous studies (Shehadeh et al., 2009); (Donald E Powers & Fowles, 1996), the study also revealed that students tended to prefer a more extended time condition as they have better opportunities for planning and revising. Although research has so far shown clear preference amongst examinees for a more extended test time condition, no studies whatsoever have found that such perceptions affect their performance outcomes.

Conclusion

Upon the research questions proposed within the current study, it was found that overall, students' academic writing performance appeared to be insignificantly different under the long (50-min) and short (30-min) condition based on the IELTS rating scale and the discourse measures. However, it was also apparent that students' scores under a long time condition increased in terms of fluency. Complexity was also found to increase, yet it was very marginal, thus making it hard to conclude. Despite the insignificant differences in their scores, participants were confident and believed that they produced better quality essays under more extended time conditions.

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